

DEVELOPMENT OF UNCONVENTIONAL AND LOGICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. This article discusses the development of non-traditional and logical thinking in children using TRIZ technology in the education of preschool children. TRIZ technology allows us to raise and educate an enterprising child. The purpose of using this technology in kindergarten is, on the one hand, to develop thinking qualities such as flexibility, mobility, consistency; on the other hand - search activity, striving for novelty; is to develop speech and creative imagination.

Key words: preschool education, preschool age, personality, TRIZ pedagogy, theory of solving inventive problems, level of school preparation, creative approach, mathematical education.

The formation of elementary mathematical concepts plays a major role in the mental education of a preschool child and in the development of his intellect. The problem of teaching mathematics to children is of great importance in modern life. This is explained by the rapid development of scientific and technical and information and communication technologies and their penetration into various fields of knowledge. According to psychologists, the development of mathematical education is complex and exciting [1].

G.S. Altshuller started work on creating TRIZ in 1946. His ideas were that invention can be taught like any other type of human activity. Indeed, creativity is the creation of something new. The purpose of TRIZ-pedagogy is to form strong thinking and educate a creative person who is prepared to solve complex problems in various spheres of activity. TRIZ pedagogy as a scientific-pedagogical direction was formed in Russia in the late 80s.

Thanks to M. Shusterman and A. Shub, who developed the methodology according to the age characteristics of 4-7-year-old children, TRIZ elements began to be studied in preschool education [2].

Scientists say that the level of a child's readiness for school is mainly related to the child's social maturity, which is manifested in the desire to occupy a new place in society, to carry out socially important and socially significant activities[1]. When starting school, the child should be ready not only to acquire knowledge, but also to completely restructure the whole way of life. N.U.Bikboeva and others [3], G.E.Dzhanpeisova [4], M.Jumaev [1] touched upon the issues of mathematical modeling technologies, use of ready-made models,

independent model creation. A.N. Mirzakarimova in her article emphasizes the effectiveness of TRIZ technology, at the same time, translates the acronym TRIZ into Uzbek as the theory of determining creativity [5].

TRIZ pedagogy is aimed at forming a strong mindset prepared to solve complex problems in various fields of activity and educating a creative and inventive person. The difference from the well-known tools of problem-based education is the use of world experience in creating inventive problem-solving methods. Of course, this experience will be revised and adapted to the goals of pedagogy. Methods of solving invention problems primarily mean techniques and algorithms developed within the framework of TRIZ; as well as well-known methods such as brainstorming, synectics, morphological analysis, the method of focal objects.

Modern TRIZ pedagogy includes courses designed for people of all age groups, from preschool children. A characteristic feature of working with each age group is the selection of age-appropriate inventive activity objects. Thus, toys, problems and examples, riddles, proverbs, open games and hakazos can be the object of activity for children of preschool age.

The tools used in TRIZ pedagogy are initially based on the method of searching for problems, which brings the technology closer to the developing education. Common features of these technologies:

- the idea of improving education and developing education;
- an approach based on educational activity;
- focus on the formation of theoretical generalizations;
- dialogic form of communication between the pedagogue and the student;
- use of problem tasks in teaching;

In order to develop creative abilities, TRIZ teachers around the world have collected teaching, invention and research tasks in areas such as physics, biology, ecology, art, technology and business.

Finding and inventing solutions to problems is exciting for preschoolers, and pride in the solution is the best motivator. We need to teach children of this age the skills of not being afraid to make mistakes or give wrong opinions in the formation of elementary mathematical ideas through TRIZ technology.

Thus, it is necessary to teach the future specialist to make decisions in difficult choice situations, to systematically perceive the world as a combination of various tasks. If a person can see a problematic situation, create a problem out of it, and approach its solution not only by learned algorithms, but also by non-standard methods, using not only the knowledge in his special field and the

accumulated experience of other specialists, then such a person can be called a highly qualified specialist.

In TRIZ pedagogy, experience has been collected in teaching methods for solving creative problems for different age groups - from preschool children to students and adult specialists. Special methods of inventive activity cannot be mastered effectively without skills:

- not seeing the unspecified characteristics of objects and events, hidden sources for problem solving;
- mastering the apparatus of formal logic in conditions of insufficient knowledge;
- highlight the main thing and ask questions that reveal its essence;
- creating a system of putting forward hypotheses (creating consciously) and testing experiments;
- work with contradictions;
- free use of a wide area of various analogies;

create a different type of classification.

Psychological studies conducted in European educational institutions show that almost all children have creative potential, which should be effectively developed through systematic lessons. Children effectively use the skills and developed abilities they have learned in their daily life. But how to determine which activities and exercises develop a child's creativity and which ones do not? This can be explained by comparing divergent (creative) thinking and convergent thinking, which develops in most preschool educational organizations when pedagogues propose problems and tasks that usually have the correct answer in the minds of students. With such a comparison, children's answers are evaluated according to the following main criteria:

- degree of accuracy of the answer;
- level of detail;
- speed;
- accuracy and degree of compliance with the prescribed form of the answer (for written assignments);
- scope of search for solutions;
- number of solution options;

The results of tasks assigned to preschool children were evaluated in individual and group performances. The traditional system of teaching children reduces internal motivation and natural interest. It is especially important to interest children in the process of forming elementary mathematical ideas.

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